

THE PROCESS OF TRANSLATION AS A SPEECH COMMUNICATION TYPE.

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Abstract. *The paper deals with the language translation process. The language translation process is a complex and intricate endeavor that involves bridging linguistic and cultural gaps to convey a message accurately and effectively in another language. It requires a deep understanding of both the source and target languages, as well as a keen awareness of cultural nuances.*

Keywords: *"golden age", global movements, speech activity, an artistic and aesthetic impact, translated section, friendly attitude, extremely awkward, accidental (unintentional), interlingual communication, communicative equivalence.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается процесс языкового перевода. Процесс языкового перевода — это сложная и запутанная работа, которая предполагает преодоление языковых и культурных разрывов для точной и эффективной передачи сообщения на другом языке. Он требует глубокого понимания как исходного, так и целевого языков, а также тонкого понимания культурных нюансов.*

Ключевые слова: *"золотой век", глобальные движения, речевая деятельность, художественно-эстетическое воздействие, переводной отрезок, доброжелательное отношение, крайне неловкий, случайный (непреднамеренный), межъязыковое общение, коммуникативная эквивалентность.*

The end of the XX century is considered to be the "golden age" of oral interpretation, which has become a very important and widespread form of human activity due to the rapid development, especially in the nineties of the XX century, in the field of science and technological advances (simultaneous translation devices, audio and video equipment, computers, the Internet, etc.). And in 1953, Pierre-François Caillé founded the International Federation of Interpreters in Paris, which represents more than fifty countries today. This is a professional, non-political, non-commercial organization that aims to unite the translation organizations of different countries.

The world map has seen the emergence of many new nation-states, as well as numerous international organizations and global movements. The rapid growth of science and technology has caused a huge need for information exchange. The volume of international trade, diplomatic activity, and international correspondence increased tremendously. Cultural ties between people have expanded, international tourism has become a large-scale activity. All these changes in the life of mankind caused the need for translations and translators. Translation agencies and publishing houses of translated literature began to appear. Nowadays, according to UNESCO, around 40 thousand translated editions are published annually in the world, i.e. more than a hundred books a day. The rapid increase in the role of translation activity in the XX century could not but arouse the interest of researchers, however, it was only by the middle of the XX century that the translation process became the object of extensive scientific study.

The linguists focused on the semantic meaning of linguistic units and speech acts, the relationship between language and mind, reality, society and culture. There appeared new linguistic disciplines and fields of research, such as psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, text linguistics, speech act theory. Due to these developments, the requirements for the accuracy of translations have increased considerably. Studies of a special kind of speech activity, which is

called translation in Russian, started to take shape as an independent linguistic discipline only from the beginning of the second half of the XX century. Thus, the linguistic science of translation is still very young. It does not even have a generally accepted name until now. Different researchers can find, for example, such terms as "translation studies", "translatology", "translation theory". The need for scientific understanding of the translation process was also determined by the need for a mass training of interpreters. The time has passed when only especially gifted people who had mastered the ability to translate on their own could be engaged in translation. To meet the enormous demand for translators, translation schools, faculties, and institutes were established in many countries, which had the goal of training a significant number of translators of sufficiently high qualification in a fixed period of time.

While investigating translation as a special type of speech communication, targeting translation theory is not limited to the analysis of its linguistic mechanism, because translation is not only the interaction of languages, but also the interaction of cultures, as it has already been said. The problems of translation drew attention of many German cultural figures - A. Schlegel, I. Goethe, J. Grimm, W. Humboldt and others. W. Humboldt, who expressed doubts about the ability of successful translation in a letter to Schlegel, became widely known, because, according to his opinion, "the translator must inevitably fall into one of two pitfalls, adhering too precisely either to his original at the expense of the taste and language of his own people, or to the originality of his own people at the expense of his original".

Let us consider the main types of translation according to two classifications suggested by V. N. Komissarov. A genre and stylistic classification imply the following types of translation: 1. Artistic translation - translation of works of fiction, the purpose of which is to create a speech work capable of having an artistic and aesthetic impact on the reader. Analysis of translations of literary works shows that it is typical for them to deviate from the maximum possible semantic accuracy in favour of artistic translation. For example: The mountain tops were hidden in a grey waste of sky... (A. Cronin).

The verb sank conveys well here the immensity of the vault of heaven, expressed by the English verb in the passive voice of were hidden. Subspecies of artistic translation: translation of poetry, plays, prose, songs. 2. Informational (special) translation - translation of texts whose main function is to provide information. These are materials of scientific, business, general political, everyday life. This should also include translation of detective stories, travel descriptions, essays, where purely informational narration prevails. Psycholinguistic classification takes into account the way of perception of the original and creation of the translation text - written or oral. Accordingly, the following types of translation are distinguished: 1. Written translation.

It is a type of translation in which the speech works united in the act of interlingual communication (the original and the target text) appear in the process of translation as fixed texts to which the translator can refer repeatedly. Written translation may be: a) full; b) abstract; c) annotative. In abstract and annotative translation, the text is compressed and not translated in its entirety. Abstract translation - translation of separate parts of the text, whereby the text is subjected to significant compression (10-20 per cent of the text volume should remain). When translating an abstract, the basic compositional structure of the text is retained; digressions, examples, repetitions, author's remarks are removed, sometimes whole paragraphs, separate sentences, parts of a sentence. The order of work on the translation-essay: - familiarise yourself with the text; - make markings with a pencil - use square brackets to select fragments for translation; - translate the selected fragments. Translation-Annotation is a summary of the content and features of a text.

Unlike an abstract, an abstract gives an idea of the main topic of the text and the list of issues it addresses. An abstract does not allow citation due to its extreme brevity. In terms of content and purpose, a distinction is made: - short annotations (they include a header and 3-4 sentences; they do not give a critical evaluation - only information); - extended (recommendatory) annotations (they contain information and evaluation of the text). Rules of translation-annotation layout: 1) an annotation header is given (includes bibliographic description, author's indication, title, output data of the text - year of publication, page); 2) the main text should contain three points: a) summarising the theme of the whole text; b) listing the main subthemes; c) formulating the main idea of the text (two sentences). 2. Interpretation. It is subdivided into subtypes, taking into account circumstances of various kinds: a) simultaneous interpretation is simultaneous work of the speaker and the interpreter (with an acceptable lag of 2-3 seconds between the interpreter and the speaker). Simultaneous interpreting is a complex type of interpreting, as it requires the interpreter to be able to perform heterogeneous speech acts simultaneously: to listen to a speech in one language, to translate it into another language and to speak in that language, without losing pace with the speaker's speech. Synchronisation of all three actions is associated with extensive memory work, intense attention, the need to perform speech compression, to predict the next segments of the original text, to correct wrong predictions, to make instant decisions, etc.; b) consecutive (paragraph-phrase) translation implies translation of 2-3 phrases each; c) translation from a sheet of paper (the interpreter receives the text to be translated and immediately performs the translation without preliminary preparation); d) bilateral translation (the interpreter works with two participants at once); e) multilateral translation (the interpreter works with two participants at once); f) multilateral translation (the interpreter works with two participants at once); g) bilateral translation (the interpreter works with two participants at once). The main difference between interpretation and translation is the impossibility of comparing the translated text with the original and correcting it.

Time plays an important role in the process of translation and interpretation. When translating, the process of translation is not limited by a fixed time frame. The interpreter can stop the translation at any time, return to an already translated section, refer to dictionaries or consult specialists. In interpreting, the interpreter's actions are strictly limited in time by the pace of the speaker's speech and the need to translate simultaneously with the speaker or immediately after the speaker has stopped. Sometimes the interpreter has to omit some details of the message being translated, compress or shorten the text of the translation. Another difference between translation and interpreting is that the interpreter deals with different parts of the original when translating. Translation and interpreting also differ in the nature of the relationship with the participants of interlingual communication. Therefore, special attention in the theory of interpreting is paid to the normative requirements to the interpreter's speech - clear articulation, even rhythm, correct accent placement, obligatory semantic and structural completeness of phrases, which ensure full perception of information by the listeners.

The process of translation as a speech communication consists of two stages that proceed directly one after the other - analysis (perception) and synthesis (speaking). When translating all types of spoken language in informal communication, the first and foremost focus should be on the transfer of meaning rather than on the mechanical translation of individual words. Always try to find the meaning! The most intolerant situation in interpreting is the interpreter's silence, when after the completion of an utterance there is a long pause instead of a confident and quick reaction in the calm of a tense expectation. The eyes are fixed on the poor person and it becomes extremely

awkward for everyone. If the interpreter is still unable to avoid this uncomfortable situation, the following is recommended: - One can improvise using key words and say something that does not contradict the situation and is appropriate for any occasion, and then try to adjust the translation as the situation progresses. Therefore, the interpreter should always have introductory words and phrases to fill the pause of misunderstanding.

- You can apologise and ask for a repeat, referring to noise or other disturbing objective factors (this option is less advisable). - It is possible, without showing that there was a hiccup, to continue working and correct your mistake in the course of the conversation. In these circumstances, the behaviour of the speaker, i.e. the sender of the information, plays an important role, who can: - realise that the translation is "sticking", repeat the previous information as if nothing had happened, adding new information, which will give the interpreter an opportunity to save face and correct the mistake; - turn everything into a joke, encourage the interpreter, calmly, more clearly and slowly repeat what was said. 16 It is inadmissible to demonstrate the "kitchen of translation" by using the phrases "I don't understand", "how is it...", "oh, I forgot", "I don't remember further", etc. A professional should not start a translation with adjectival sentences, question words and interjections. It is unacceptable to abandon sentences halfway through, to leave them incomplete intonationally and grammatically. The interpreter should not show his/her sympathies or antipathies; he/she should convey information to the addressee clearly and effectively, without intonation or lexicon showing his/her attitude to a particular issue. In the course of negotiations, it is more acceptable to keep a good-natured dispassion, as if smoothing out the emotional differences of the participants. In conclusion, let us formulate the following points for the interpreter: 1. The translator must realise that he or she does not influence and is not responsible for the sender's original information, but is professionally, morally and even legally responsible for his or her translation. 2. Never panic or pass out in any situation. 3. Translate not words but thoughts. Thus, the complexity of this or that type of translation activity is determined not only by the conditions of functioning of the translator's mental mechanisms, but also by the nature of the source texts typical for this type of translation, the requirements that are imposed on the translated texts, and the linguistic features of the translated material (terms, stamps, situational clichés, figurative expressions). The problem of context has been repeatedly raised and solved in the works of many linguists. The context is understood as the direct lexical context of a given word or expression in speech, the context that makes the meaning of the word or expression clear or gives it some new shades. It is clear to the translator that no less difficult than the construction of a phrase is the choice of a suitable word-equivalent. The translator must constantly balance various lexical possibilities, synonyms, in order to choose a word (rarely two or three words) that can sufficiently reproduce the meaning of the original. At the same time, all sorts of various aspects pass through the translator's mind to make the final choice. This is why contextualisation is so important. When looking for a suitable equivalent, we always have in mind a word in context or a word that is conditioned by all the preceding and following statements. 20 There are the following types of context: 1. Linguistic context is the linguistic environment of the use of a particular unit of language. To the extent of this notion, a distinction is made: 1) Narrow context (or microcontext), i.e. the context of a sentence - linguistic units that constitute the environment of a given unit within the sentence [Komissarov, 1990, p. 142]. Narrow context, in its turn, is: a) a syntactic context, i.e. the syntactic construction in which the given word, word combination or (adjectival) sentence is used; b) a lexical context, i.e. a set of specific lexical units, words and stable word combinations in the environment of which the given unit is found. 2) Broad context

(or macro-context) - the linguistic environment of a given unit which goes beyond the sentence; it is a textual context, i.e. a set of linguistic units surrounding the given unit within the limits lying outside the given sentence, in other words, in adjacent sentences. The exact limits of the broad context cannot be specified; it may be the context of a group of sentences, a paragraph, a chapter, or even of the whole work as a whole (e.g., a story or a novel). 2. Situational (extra-linguistic) context - the setting, time and place to which the utterance refers; any facts of real reality, knowledge of which helps the translator to correctly interpret the meanings of language units in the utterance. The conditions of the context may induce the translator to refuse to use even a single correspondence in translation. For example, geographical names have permanent correspondences, which, as a rule, are created by imitating the sound of the foreign language name in translation. The name of the American city of New Haven (Connecticut) is regularly rendered into Russian as New Haven. But in the translation of Fitzgerald's novel *The Great Gatsby*, the translator E. Kalashnikova refused to use the constant correspondence and translated the sentence I graduated from New Haven in 1915 as I graduated from Yale University in 1915. The context clearly shows that the name of the city in the original is used in a figurative sense - instead of an educational institution located in this city. And knowledge of reality suggested to the translator that the reference is to the widely known in the USA Yale University, which is located in New Haven. Since this fact may be unknown to the Russian reader, replacing the name of the city with the name of the university helps to ensure the communicative equivalence of the translation. The context clearly shows that the name of the city in the original is used in a figurative sense - instead of an educational institution located in that city. And the translator's knowledge of reality told him that this is the widely known Yale University in the USA, which is located in New Haven. Since the Russian reader may not be aware of this fact, replacing the name of the city with the name of the university helps to ensure communicative equivalence of the translation. Context plays the most significant role in revealing the polysemousness of linguistic units. Not counting cases of intentional or accidental (unintentional) ambiguity, context serves as a means that "removes" all but one of the meanings of a particular polysemantic unit. In this way, the context gives a particular language unit single-valuedness and makes it possible to choose one of several equivalents of this unit that potentially exist in the target language. Of course, the role of context is far from being limited to the resolution of multiple meanings of words and other linguistic units, but its most important function is precisely this. In the process of translation, it is sometimes sufficient to take into account the syntactic context of a unit, in particular a word, in order to choose an equivalent. Thus, the verb *burn* can be translated into Russian as *burn* and as *burn*, the choice of correspondence being entirely determined by the syntactic context in which the English word is used: in a non-transitive construction (in the absence of a direct complement) *burn* is translated as *burn*, in a transitive construction (in the presence of a direct complement or a form of the passive voice) - as *burn*. Cf: The candle burns - The candle burns; He did not burn the papers. This is a very common case for English. Cf: sink, drown; drive, to drive, to chase. More often, however, the choice of an equivalent takes into account only the lexical context. Thus, English *look* in combination with the adjective *angry* means *look*, and in combination with the adjective *European* means *look* (e.g. The town has a European look); English *way* in combination with *to the town* means *road*, and in combination with *doing it* - *way* or *method*. There are many examples of this kind. To illustrate the role of the narrow lexical context in selecting a translation match, consider the following English sentences containing the multi meaning noun *attitude*: Does not have a friendly attitude towards all - He has a friendly attitude towards everyone. There is no sign of any

change in the attitudes of the two sides. He did not stand there in a threatening attitude. Is not known for his anti-Soviet attitudes - He is known for his anti-Soviet attitudes. Thus, the context allows us to overcome semantic discrepancies caused by the mismatch between the structure of the semantic fields of the source and target languages.

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